

A Lesson from QIIME: Free Massive Multiplayer Online Bioinformatics Pipeline for Self-Taught Coder

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With the advancement of the internet, countless online and technology-based education methods have emerged. Professional institutions have made massive open online courses (MOOC) and online degree programs, as well as formal and structured learning methods¹. However, non-formal and less structured methods –such as a Google or YouTube search, and community forums such as Reddit or Discord– should not be undermined^{2,3}. These platforms encourage learners to go online and connect with other people. Even top universities such as Harvard, MIT, Stanford have made their courses available online –either through paid MOOC or for free on YouTube.

The best example is the QIIMETM, a bioinformatic software pipeline that profiles microbiome from metagenomic DNA data (biomarker genes such as 16S-rRNA and 18S-rRNA or shotgun metagenomic data)^{4,5}. Since the host's microbiome has a strong correlation with the host's health and well-being^{6,7}. QIIME has been used in countless biomedical research : gut⁸⁻¹⁰, oral^{8,9}, skin¹¹, eye¹², etc. Focusing on profiling changes in the gut microbiome and detection of certain pathogenic bacteria (notably *Firmicutes/Bacteroidetes* ratio)^{6,7}. It has been the gold standard in microbiome analysis until this day. As of writing, QIIME has been utilized in scientific papers (>50,000); scientific patents (>2,000); and even in clinical trials (>50). This information is based on a personal communication with Dr. Greg Caporaso, the first author of the original QIIME publication (via QIIME 2 Forum)¹³. Without the internet and the open source concept, willingness to share knowledge online with a complete stranger –how else could a graduate student from across the world get information from one QIIME's main creators?

QIIME is open-source (free) and runs best on Linux operating system (free). Thus, with an adequate computer and internet connection, anyone in the world can install, learn, and use QIIME for free. The minimum requirements for QIIME2 is only 8 GB of RAM, which most standard laptops currently meet). The original QIIME was first released in 2010 and was actively maintained—with regular updates, bug fixes, and community support via forums,

documentation, and tutorial videos—through 2018⁴. Then, QIIME2 was released in 2018, migrating from Python 2 to Python 3, with significant improvements in microbiota classification accuracy⁵.

In the biomedical field; gold standard methods such as polymerase chain reaction and western blot, are hard to learn without access to the material and laboratory. In order to get: samples, reagents (antibody, primer, polymerase, kit, etc.), equipment, instrumentation, and instructors, someone needs to go to the lab. With bioinformatics, it can be done anywhere regardless of the learner's background. The only prerequisites are a working computer and an internet connection. Thus, anyone can kickstart or further their education and career in the biomedical field through online (most of which are free) training in bioinformatics.

Based on my own experience: during my first week of graduate school, my principal investigator suddenly tasked me to learn and establish a bacterial genome sequencing, assembly, and analysis for the lab. I have no experience in coding; I was a bioprocess engineering graduate with zero experience in coding. Even during the interview process, this task was not mentioned.

The funding was running out. The cost for bacterial genome, sequencing, and assembly by a biotech company in South Korea is 1,000,000 KRW; the cost of only sequencing was 500,000 KRW. Even though the company used open source softwares to perform the tasks¹⁷⁻²³. With a bit of resilience and a free online course, 50% of the budget can be saved per bacterial sample.

The main problem was that there were no bioinformaticians in the lab. I have no instructor in the lab or school. My strategy was first to read scientific publications and asked AI assistance what software to learn to perform certain tasks. Then, I searched YouTube for the installation guides and software tutorial²⁴. Usually tutorials have step-by-step instructions with a dataset downloaded from NCBI open database. However, there were always errors that were not discussed; this is where forums and AI assistance come in handy^{25,26}. As a result of using the previously mentioned methods, the system that I built worked, and we published publications.

In conclusion, much of the bioinformatic software used in research and commercial are usually open-source. Made by researchers who published it in peer-reviewed journals. It has been a consistent and sustainable trend in the bioinformatics field. Each software came with its respective documentation and forum (mostly GitHub) for successful installation and troubleshooting. With this approach, anyone can do it, regardless of their access to top universities, economic background, nationality, etc.

However, any learner who chooses the “self-taught” route must be careful. Although this

method is faster, it is chaotic. The learner can get the job done, but some key concepts can be missed. And not all communities are well-managed like the QIIME community (QIIME forum even has a job opening notice).

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